

ON THE ISSUE OF SEXUAL DEVELOPMENT DEFICIT IN ADOLESCENT GIRLS

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Preserving the health of adolescent girls is considered a promising contribution to the reproductive, intellectual, economic and social reserves of society. **Purpose of the study:** to compare the severity of sexual development and its delay in teenage girls from different regions of our Republic.

Materials and methods of research. To determine the frequency and prevalence of mental retardation among adolescent girls, we examined 85 school and specialized college students aged 13-18 years in the Khorezm region and the Tashkent region.

Research results. BMI in patients with mental retardation indicates weight loss: at 14, 17 and 18 years old, this indicator is identical to the BMI of girls with normal sexual development; in the subgroups of 15 and 16 year old girls it was 18.48 ± 0.57 versus 20.01 ± 0.2 and 19.31 ± 0.54 versus 21.55 ± 0.22 ($P < 0.05$).

Sexual development score for mental retardation of I-III degree. represented by the degree of severity of axillary (Ax), pubic (P) hair growth, as well as the degree of development of the mammary glands (Ma). The total score of these indicators for stage I mental retardation at the age of 13 to 16 years varies from 1.89 ± 0.04 to 4.67 ± 0.86 , which corresponds to a lag in sexual development of girls with normal puberty by 2-2.9 of the year. With stage II mental retardation at the age of 13 to 18 years, the BPR changes from 0.7 ± 0.13 to 5.25 ± 2.03 , which corresponds to a delay in sexual development of 2.9-4 years and with stage III mental retardation. BDP at the age of 14 to 18 years increases from 1.32 ± 0.12 to 3.64 ± 0.61 , which indicates a delay in sexual development of more than 4 years.

Secondary disturbances of menstrual function against the background of signs of sexual infantilism are clinical signs of mental retardation. Among the girls we examined, secondary amenorrhea was detected in 22.9%, opsomenorrhea - 43.1%, long-term unsettled menstrual cycles (more than two years) - 34.0%, of which those accompanied by juvenile bleeding - 9.2%.

The lowest degree of uterine hypoplasia was determined in patients with mental retardation, but the difference with similar parameters in girls from the control group was significant in all age subgroups, with the exception of 14-year-old girls ($P < 0.05$). The dynamic increase in uterine body length at the age of 14-18 years in these comparison groups was 3.8 and 6.5 mm. The maximum increase in the longitudinal dimensions of the uterus in patients with mental retardation and adolescent girls with normal sexual development was detected at the age of 13 to 16 years: with mental retardation stage I. - 10.5 mm, with stage II DSD - 13 mm, in the control group - 7.8 mm.

Thus, a comparative assessment of the characteristics of sexual development in girls with mental retardation revealed varying degrees of deficiency in sexual development, which manifests itself depending on the degree and form of the disease. Ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs is a diagnostic method that allows identifying signs of sexual infantilism in erased forms of pathology.

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